

Open and Programmable Accelerators for Data-intensive Applications in the Cloud

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Motivation.....	7
1.2 Purpose and Scope of the Document	7
1.3 Non-Objectives.....	7
1.4 Structure of the Document	8
2. Accelerated Cloud Systems Architecture.....	9
2.1 Traditional Cloud Systems Stacks.....	9
2.2 The Accelerator Layer	9
2.3 Integrating the Accelerator Layer	10
3. Accelerated Cloud Management Architecture.....	12
3.1 Traditional Cloud Management Stack	12
3.2 Managing I/O Accelerators.....	13
3.3 Integrating the Accelerator Management.....	13
4. Detailed Flows.....	15
4.1 Server-level Flows.....	15
4.2 Device-level Flows	16
5. Conclusions	18
Bibliography	19

List of Figures

Figure 1: A traditional layered cloud application (left) and examples of systems at each layer (right).	9
Figure 2: The accelerator access layer can be integrated into the HW/OS layer from Fig. 1.	9
Figure 3: Internal view of the SSD-OS and Menschen.	10
Figure 4: Example of how accelerator-layer features in one layer support features on the next layer.	11
Figure 5: A traditional cloud management stack (right) and exmaples of systems at each layer (left).	12
Figure 6: Extending the fundamental services from Fig. 5 to work on accelerators.....	13
Figure 7: Example of how accelerator-management features in one layer support features in the next.....	14
Figure 8: In traditional data center servers, the CPU becomes the bottleneck.	15
Figure 9: Processing flows on accelerators avoid the issue.	15
Figure 10: Example of how to support the SQL-over-Parquet service in Fig. 4.....	16

List of Abbreviations

CPU Central Processing Unit
GPU Graphics Processing Unit
NIC Network Interface Card
NDP Near-Data Processing
OS Operating System
SSD Solid-State Drive

Executive Summary

Data-intensive applications primarily consist of *data flows* that access data from storage or network devices and apply a series of transformations to them. The CHORYS project aims at accelerating these applications by a deceptively simple proposition: to allow data flows to perform transformations directly within the storage and network devices. We achieve this by equipping these devices with a combination of slightly modified RISC-V CPUs and specialized hardware units known as *accelerators*. These accelerators are designed to excel at specific, commonly used data manipulation primitives, referred to as *data patterns*. In Deliverable D4.1 (“Design Space for RISC-V Extensions”), we outlined our approach to designing and prototyping these data pattern accelerators. In this deliverable, we discuss how the resulting accelerated storage and network infrastructure can serve as a foundation for building new or enhancing existing cloud environments.

In summary, we propose integrating our devices into standard rack-based servers commonly used by hyperscalers [5]. We will equip our devices with an access layer similar to that of CPUs, conferring our devices with the ability to load programs, isolate between them (e.g., for virtualization), and monitor their resource consumption (e.g., for billing purposes). This access layer allows hyperscalers to then integrate Near-Data Processing (NDP) capabilities into their service layers. For instance, storage services, such as file systems, could be enhanced to include programs that execute during file read or write operations. Similarly, layers for network communication could utilize this capability when transmitting or receiving data. The anticipated net effect is that by simply swapping out regular devices for our computational ones and adjusting the service layers, the platform will gain computational capacity and improve efficiency.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

We are currently facing an unprecedented computational crunch [13]. This situation is primarily driven by the demand for hardware in machine learning, particularly Graphics Processing Unit (GPU), but it also impacts the hardware that supplies data to these GPUs. The CHORYS project is developing two key devices to address this issue: a Solid-State Drive (SSD) known as OpenSSD-V and a Network Interface Card (NIC) called OpenNIC-V. As essential I/O devices, they are designed to store and transport data to GPUs and Central Processing Unit (CPU) efficiently.

This is not, however, the primary reason our devices are competitive. What sets them apart is their ability to process data directly, rather than merely transmitting it to CPUs and GPUs for processing, which alleviates the burden on those units. Consequently, using our devices instead of traditional SSDs and NICs enhances a platform's computational power while maintaining the same physical footprint—among other advantages. **How should these new platforms be designed?**

1.2 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document lays the groundwork for this question to be answered. Our premise is that the Cloud—large data centers with hundreds of thousands of somewhat uniform rack-mounted servers—is and will continue to be the prevalent architecture to deliver large computational platforms. Our focus, therefore, is on how to position our devices as new building blocks within cloud environments and, importantly, how existing cloud software stacks can integrate and benefit from the features our devices offer.

Central to this discussion are the *application acceleration* capabilities of the CHORYS's devices. This feature allows our devices to process some very common data manipulation patterns faster than CPUs or GPUs, while consuming less energy. We credit this efficiency to a combination of specialized hardware we are designing, modified RISC-V CPUs that our devices carry, and software primitives to expose them to applications. In this document, we will explore how cloud applications can interact with our primitives and how hyperscalers—the companies behind large cloud infrastructures—can effectively manage a substantial number of our devices.

1.3 Non-Objectives

While there are many commonalities across different cloud stacks, each hyperscaler's offer is peculiar. We are going to refer to random examples of cloud infrastructure software to make the discussion more concrete, but we are not endorsing any vendor or comparing different vendors' stacks. We note also that the integration between cloud stacks and our hardware and software infrastructure occurs at a very low level within the stack. The benefits of this integration, however, can propagate to different systems. We focus on integration aspects in this document and mention in high-level terms how it can benefit other systems. It is not our goal to provide detailed designs of the latter.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this deliverable is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a traditional Cloud Systems stack and discusses the integration of the CHORYS devices within it. Section 3 provides a similar analysis, but this time, it focuses on the Management stack commonly found in cloud environments. In Section 4, we describe the architectural changes that occur within a datacenter-class server, which is the fundamental building block for larger cloud infrastructures. We conclude this document in Section 5, where we summarize our findings and mention further discussions we will present in upcoming deliverables.

2 Accelerated Cloud Systems Architecture

2.1 Traditional Cloud Systems Stacks

The services offered by hyperscalers represent just the visible tip of a deep and extensive stack of systems [5]. In Fig. 1, we attempt to simplify this stack for the purposes of our discussion. We do so by organizing these systems into the different classes of applications they enable. The figure presents two examples of applications: a database system and a message queue. We selected these applications because they rely on storage and networking functionalities, respectively, which can benefit from the OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V, as we will discuss.

Figure 1: A traditional layered cloud application (left) and examples of systems at each layer (right).

The applications at the top of the stack leverage functionalities provided by external services that are both visible and purchasable by cloud users. For instance, a database may utilize an object store or a block store, while a message queue likely depends on group communication services. This represents the extent to which external users interact with the cloud. However, the external systems are far from the bottom of the stack. They rely on proprietary systems such as distributed file systems [8], lock servers [6], log servers [21], and remote procedure call functionality [11], among others. These systems remain unseen by external users, and companies often treat them as trade secrets, despite publishing high-level descriptions.

These systems stand to gain the most from our devices, providing new hyperscalers a pathway to catch up with established companies. They depend on a commoditized base layer, predominantly featuring an Operating System (OS) (typically Linux) or some form of hypervisor (such as Xen [26]). We propose that by integrating our devices at the base of the stack and enabling them to export services to the upper layers, we can facilitate an advanced stack that runs in parallel with and benefits from a traditional stack.

2.2 The Accelerator Layer

Adding the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V to the base of the stack involves providing resource management features for these devices, similar to an OS, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The OpenNIC-V will enhance a foundational software called Menshen [24]. We will delve into this functionality when discussing the management aspects of the stack.

Figure 2: The accelerator access layer can be integrated into the HW/OS layer from Fig. 1.

For now, it suffices to note that Menshen enables programs to intercept and manage data flowing through a network card. The OpenSSD-V will also utilize an OS currently under active development, aptly named SSD OS. Figure 3 illustrates these OS's conceptual view, showing that both an SSD and NIC take data from Flash memory or the network, respectively, and move that data to the host—and vice-versa—potentially staging it on some local memory. As the figure also shows, the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V carry a combination of RISC-V CPUs and accelerators, strategically placed to allow programs running on one or both of them to intercept and alter data flow.

Figure 3: Internal view of the SSD-OS and Menshen.

Herein lies the core of the innovation of the Chorys project. Processing the flow could only have been done on the CPU or GPU, which would require all the data to be transferred to these units. This transfer process is time-consuming and power-intensive, particularly when dealing with large datasets common in modern machine learning or big data applications.

These computations are deemed *reductive* when their output is smaller than the input, such as in cases of data filtering or aggregation [19]. Performing reductive computations on the device avoids moving data to the host, and produce performance benefits, but they are not the only advantageous operation. Sorting, parsing, and various other data organization activities, while not necessarily reductive, can benefit from the accelerators available in our devices. The full data transfer may still occur in these instances, but processing the data on our accelerators rather than on a host CPU is more energy efficient [7]. It is also faster, since the accelerator is designed to perform in hardware what the CPU would have done in software.

2.3 Integrating the Accelerator Layer

The fundamental change we are suggesting to a traditional cloud services stack (cf. Section 2.1) is the addition of a new hardware building block: the CHORYS devices. Their OSs will enable the base layer to manage the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V similarly to how it handles CPUs. We describe how the features introduced by our devices can support mechanisms on the upper layer through an example in Figure 4—ultimately showing that the benefits extend to the external and application layers of the stack, where the commercial services of a hyperscaler operate.

The OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V support the efficient execution of data primitives on flows coming through these devices. We will discuss an example with more details later in this document, but at a high level, this capability allows our devices to parse and filter data stored in the system effectively. Hyperscalers typically implement distributed file systems on their Internal Services Layer that can read/write to a large number of large files (e.g., [8]). These systems' API could be extended to leverage our devices and apply a program during a read or a write. For example, during a read, the program can parse the data it reads and evaluate a certain

Initial System Architecture

Figure 4: Example of how accelerator-layer features in one layer support features on the next layer.

predicate on the data, discarding the data that does not meet the criteria. This way, the data returned on a read operation would be the result of the program rather than the original data. With this change, a traditional distributed file system can become NDP-enabled one.

Moving one layer up in the services stack, the typical Object Store service that hyperscalers offer can be based on a distributed file system. In turn, if the latter is NDP-enabled, the Object Store could offer the possibility to run programs using this feature. There are precedents of known Object Stores attempting to do so: Amazon AWS S3 once supported what it called *S3 Select*, with some form of near-data processing [4]. This feature, however, has been deprecated. We can only speculate whether they miss the key aspect that, to be efficient, data patterns should be supported at the hardware level, as we suggest here.

Moving once again one layer up, there could be application-level services that leverage computational object stores, such as Data Lakehouses [2]. These systems support querying data with high-level languages such as SQL, without requiring the data to be loaded upfront on a Relational Database. This scenario is what Fig.4 refers to as *SQL-over-Parquet*. Parquet [1] is a popular file format that applications use to record user activities—e.g., trips on a maps application, purchases on an e-commerce platform, to cite a few.

A SQL-over-Parquet application can query the data by accessing it in the Parquet files directly. Normally, this access is expensive because processing SQL is done on a server's CPU and ingests large Parquet files. If, however, the object store underneath the system supports computations, the lakehouse can push SQL processing to this layer. The request will traverse the stack of services and will execute on our accelerated devices.

The approach we described above is just an example of the use of composition to expose the Chorys devices' features in a typical cloud stack. Other notable instances of inefficient CPU usage can be found in Machine Learning applications. For example, in Convolutional Networks—an architecture commonly employed for image processing tasks—the images used for training require pre-processing, as networks trained on raw data tend to exhibit low accuracy [18]. Typically, image pre-processing is performed on CPUs. In a manner similar to how data pattern primitives support SQL processing, we can envision additional data patterns that facilitate the manipulation of images and other data types, thereby enabling the development of machine learning training services.

3 Accelerated Cloud Management Architecture

3.1 Traditional Cloud Management Stack

An important aspect of running cloud services is the effective management of those services. The tasks that are involved in service management, such as system health monitoring and billing are, in themselves, considered cloud services. It should be unsurprising that hyper-scalers operate cloud management stacks that closely resemble the cloud application stack discussed in Section 2.1. Figure 5 illustrates the layout of common management services using the same layers we previously examined.

Figure 5: A traditional cloud management stack (right) and examples of systems at each layer (left).

Billing and dashboard (health monitoring) services are part of the customer-visible part of the stack. There are at least two critical, also user-facing services supporting them: a scheduler and a monitoring/alerting service. The scheduler is responsible for orchestrating the processes that constitute a given service [22, 23]. Informally, the number of processes in some services can grow to tens or hundreds of thousands in large data centers [15], making cluster management a complex undertaking. The dashboard plays a crucial role by collecting information about the fleet of processes launched by the scheduler and summarizing their activity [3, 9]. Most importantly, the dashboard must be capable of identifying issues with running services, such as when a service’s response time falls below acceptable thresholds.

The non-visible part of the stack encompasses some critical services as well. To be able to schedule a service across large data centers, the issue arises as to how to make—potentially large—binary files, which contain a service’s program instructions, available to any potentially free machine in the data center. Moreover, to support monitoring and alerting systems, a robust service must be implemented to collect operating data from the numerous processes in operation. These services are known as Binary Distribution and Telemetry services.

Like in the application stack in the previous section, the internal services mentioned above also rely on a fundamental layer sitting atop the hardware and operating system. In the case of the management stack, this layer performs resource management, binary loading, and process introspection capabilities. The resource management feature allows the scheduler to assign portions of a resource—e.g., an amount of memory on a server—to a specific customer process, without other customer tasks interfering with it [20]. The binary loading feature is capable of launching a process to execute any given binary. Lastly, the process introspection capability is what allows, for instance, a telemetry module to discover how many resources—once again, memory, for example—at any given moment [10].

3.2 Managing I/O Accelerators

Similar to our introduction of the OpenSSD-V and OpenNIC-V in the application stack's hardware layer, as discussed in Section 2.2, we also integrate these devices into the management stack, as illustrated in Figure 6. Importantly, we do not alter the functionality of the base layer in this process. Instead, we enhance the devices with features that allow them to function as computing elements from the perspective of cloud management. These features include the ability to set resource limits to control how much of the device a program can utilize (Resource Limits), the capability to load programs for execution (Binary Loader), and the option to query the resulting process during execution for operational data (Process Introspection).

Figure 6: Extending the fundamental services from Fig. 5 to work on accelerators.

However, there are differences between a computational device like ours and CPUs. Whereas programs in a CPU control how they access data, a program running on our devices attaches itself to one or more existing data flows. In practice, this means that resource management for the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V revolves around the data flows. Resource consumption is measured by how many flows—the allowed bandwidth—a program can access. Binary loading must indicate to which flows a program wishes to attach itself. Process introspection may reveal at what bandwidth a data flow is traversing the device and whether a program is keeping up. Once again, these differences fit into an existing framework for low-level management of a cloud hardware building block, but the new devices add peculiarities to the framework.

3.3 Integrating the Accelerator Management

Similarly to the integration of the accelerator layer on the application stack, which we described in Section 2.3, we can integrate the management of the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V in a cloud management stack via composition. We describe how to do so via an example of Dashboard, shown in Figure 7, in which we would be interested in monitoring whether our devices are keeping pace with the data flows to which they are attached. In this scenario, we consider an OpenNIC-V running a program on a high-speed flow. While the program may introduce some latency if it is unable to handle the flow's bandwidth, unbounded queuing may occur. A Dashboard application can monitor for this situation and alert system administrators as soon as a risk of prolonged queuing is detected.

The monitoring starts with the ability of the OpenNIC-V to export the rate at which a given program is operating. This rate corresponds to the instantaneous number of packets processed per second by the program. The Telemetry service is responsible for regularly probing the OpenNIC-V for this rate, leveraging the accelerator's ability to perform process introspection. The Telemetry service can store these values as time series in a database and additionally export them as a publish/subscribe stream. [17]. The stream can be captured by a Monitoring/Alerting system that is programmed to calculate the processing rate of the program on the OpenNIC-V is adequate, or otherwise issue an alert [25]. Lastly, the Dashboard displays the calculated rate, highlighting any alerts in red font to indicate issues.

Initial System Architecture

Figure 7: Example of how accelerator-management features in one layer support features in the next.

We should mention that this arrangement in the management stack could also support some form of billing service. The OpenNIC-V could keep some counters internally that could record the packet rate we described above, but also some form of variable to quantify the amount of compute being done on the card—among several other parameters upon which a cloud provider using Chorys devices may wish to build a pricing model. The primary distinction here is that the aggregation of resource consumption may occur in a less immediate manner than what is typically required in a dashboard. Ultimately, while programming Chorys devices differs from programming traditional CPU-based servers, the management processes remain consistent across both types of systems.

4 Detailed Flows

4.1 Server-level Flows

One of the most interesting aspects about the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V is that they serve as drop-in replacements for traditional SSDs and network cards in data center servers, as Figure 8 depicts. The figure also shows the other typical functional components on a server—a CPU with attached memory, and, as is common nowadays, inference and training accelerator units—and how they interact with I/O devices. The data that the CPU and these units consume or generate is handled by the devices, resulting in flows that are always mediated by the CPU. The key aspect here is that replacing an SSD with the OpenSSD-V and a NIC with the OpenNIC-V does not fundamentally alter how servers are currently designed. This tight compatibility can foster the adoption of our devices.

Figure 8: In traditional data center servers, the CPU becomes the bottleneck.

The major advantage of using the Chorys devices is how they alter the data flows inside the server. Since these devices are computational, some processes that would otherwise run on a CPU could be moved into the devices, as Figure 9 shows. With this arrangement, many computations that would require two data transfers—one from I/O to CPU and another from CPU to Inference/Training hardware—now only require a single transfer, from I/O to Inference/Training hardware, thanks to the ability of the OpenSSD-V or OpenNIC-V to perform computations over the data flows they carry.

Figure 9: Processing flows on accelerators avoid the issue.

We cannot emphasize enough the magnitude of the potential here, so we quote verbatim from a study about the cost of moving data on scientific applications: “The energy cost of data movement has been identified as one of the major limiting factors for the development of efficient and sustainable exascale systems.” [14].

There is another opportunity for optimizing the data movement. For reductive computations, such as data filtering or aggregation, the output can be significantly smaller than the input. By shifting computations to the device, we transfer the output rather than the input, resulting in a corresponding reduction in data movement, whether the output is consumed by the CPU or another unit on the server.

4.2 Device-level Flows

Shifting computations to a device is done by logically attaching a program to an otherwise naturally occurring flow on the device. For instance, using the OpenSSD-V, one might intercept a data flow generated by a read request and apply a transformation to it. Figure 10 illustrates this example and contrasts it with a standard data flow. The standard read flow appears in yellow, showcasing the transfer of data from Flash Memory—a type of persistent memory commonly used in SSDs [16]—to the host. Notably, during this transfer, the data remains unchanged.

Figure 10: Example of how to support the SQL-over-Parquet service in Fig. 4

Figure 10 also illustrates how a program can intercept the data flow, depicted in blue. The program running on an OpenSSD-V can operate on this flow in two ways: by utilizing a modified RISC-V CPU that can access the data directly or by leveraging the data pattern accelerators implemented in hardware. This example illustrates both methods in the context of parsing and filtering the data flow. Such capabilities would be particularly helpful for the SQL-over-Parquet application discussed in Section 2.3.

The program starts by performing data parsing using the corresponding data pattern accelerator. This parsing process reconstructs data records present in the stream, which are encoded in the Parquet format. The parsed records are temporarily stored in memory, accessible by the RISC-V CPU on the device. For this example, the CPU filters the records by discarding those that do not meet specified criteria. Following this, the program reconstructs the data stream in the Parquet format using another data pattern accelerator, the deparser, ensuring that the resulting stream appears as though the filtered-out records never existed.

One may wonder why different mechanisms for program execution are combined on the OpenSSD-V when a general-purpose CPU could suffice. The challenge with relying solely on a CPU is that, to compete with the CPUs found in data center servers, the device’s processor would

need to be significantly fast. Our goal is to ensure that programs moved into the device run at comparable speeds. However, incorporating such a high-performance CPU in the SSD would inevitably increase its energy consumption.

The advantage of specialized accelerators lies in their potential to be orders of magnitude more energy efficient than a CPU [7]. However, even when our selection of accelerators targets common and costly data manipulation primitives, there remains a possibility that programs may require functionalities outside this scope. By combining the accelerators with a carefully balanced RISC-V, specifically designed for our workloads, we get the best of both worlds.

5 Conclusions

In this document, we presented how to integrate the CHORYS accelerated devices into a typical cloud architecture from principles. We discussed separately how to integrate our technology into applications and the management stacks typically found in larger hyperscalers. The integration was discussed at several levels of detail: from how to use our devices in an individual server, to how to run programs in these devices, to how this ability could create new and enhance existing cloud services.

The main takeaways from these discussions are as follows:

- A cloud provider does not need to alter its architecture to adopt our innovations completely.
- They can modify existing or add a new platform- and internal-level services that utilize the NDP features of the OpenSSD-V and the OpenNIC-V.
- For applications, this means faster performance and the ability to perform a larger volume of data.
- For cloud providers, our technology can provide a competitive edge vis-a-vis more established or larger hyperscalers.

This document also laid the groundwork for discussions we will have in upcoming deliverables. It introduced the abstraction of data flows and showed examples of how to improve them using our technology. Still missing are a more complete definition of data flows, where they appear, and how to attach logic to them, which will demonstrate further why we believe they are central to our innovations. We also expect to discuss the topics we presented here in light of more specific cloud architectures (e.g., Cyso's architecture, which is one of CHORYS Project's partners, or IPCEI-CS reference architectures [12]).

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